

Research paper

Design and experimental evaluation of a topology-optimized metamaterial cell fabricated via 3D printing for enhanced energy absorption

Amir Shahmorad

School of Mechanical Engineering, Iran University of Science and Technology, Tehran, Iran

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ABSTRACT

In this study, three topology-optimized structures were constructed using polylactide (PLA) via material extrusion (MEX) to investigate their mechanical performance under compression and impact loading. The structures, named TV, TH, and TVH, underwent quasi-static compressive loading and dynamic impact testing to assess their load-bearing capacity and energy absorption characteristics. The results revealed significant differences in behavior across structural designs. While one structure exhibited the highest compressive strength, another demonstrated superior energy absorption under impact, highlighting the influence of topology on mechanical performance. For example, the weight of TV structure reduced to 50%, while these structures indicated highest compressive strength. Moreover, the weight of TH structures reduced to 30%, and these structures showed highest energy absorption. The findings indicate that topology optimization enables tailored structural responses, enabling the design of lightweight components with enhanced strength and energy dissipation.

1. Introduction

Metamaterials are engineered cellular architectures whose unconventional macroscopic behavior arises largely from their structural geometry rather than the inherent properties of the materials from which they are composed [1]. Their design methodologies generally fall into two main approaches: bio-inspired strategies that replicate efficient natural structural mechanisms [2], and optimization-based frameworks that iteratively refine topology to achieve extreme performance metrics, including enhanced strength-to-weight ratio and increased energy dissipation [3]. Due to their inherent geometric complexity, additive manufacturing—particularly advanced 3D printing—has become the most effective technique for fabricating these architectures with high fidelity, enabling precise control over unit-cell morphology and mechanical response [4].

Based on the findings of some recent studies, biomimetic and architected cellular materials have shown significant potential for improving the mechanical performance and energy absorption capability of advanced structures. Recent research has demonstrated that bioinspired lattice geometries, particularly auxetic and hierarchical designs, can effectively enhance deformation stability, impact resistance, and specific energy absorption under compressive and dynamic loading conditions. Moreover, integrating functionally graded

architectures and topology optimization strategies has been reported to improve load distribution and delay localized failure, leading to superior crashworthiness compared with conventional uniform cellular structures. These investigations also highlight that the combination of biomimetic design principles with additive manufacturing enables the fabrication of lightweight structures with tailored mechanical responses, making them suitable for applications requiring high energy absorption efficiency and structural reliability. Collectively, these studies indicate that the development of biomimetic porous metamaterials offers a promising pathway toward the design of next-generation lightweight impact-resistant structures with enhanced multifunctional performance [5–7].

Prajapati et al. [8] developed hybrid TPU-based metamaterial cells using material extrusion (MEX), reporting significant improvements in stiffness, damping capacity, and overall mechanical performance, with increased porosity further enhancing energy absorption. Hu et al. [9] examined the compressive behavior of metamaterials produced via projection micro-stereolithography (PμSL), demonstrating tunable density and nanoscale-like mechanical performance surpassing that of conventional stainless steel, with the number of cells significantly influencing compressive strength and energy absorption. Chen et al. [10] evaluated carbon-fiber-reinforced polyamide (CF/PA) metamaterials, revealing that continuous fiber composites (CCF/PA) exhibit

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: rhashemi@iust.ac.ir (R. Hashemi).

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higher stiffness, peak load, and energy absorption than short fiber counterparts (SCF/PA), and that numerical analyses closely matched experimental results.

Zhang et al. [11] studied wavy-wall metamaterials under static and dynamic compressive loading, showing that wall thickness and aspect ratio affect energy absorption and negative Poisson's ratio, with impact tests indicating reduced energy dissipation. Asman et al. [12] analyzed micro lattice structures fabricated via selective laser melting (SLM) from stainless steel L316, finding that stretched cell lattices (SCL) exhibit higher specific energy absorption (SEA), energy absorption efficiency (EAE), and yield strength compared to octet truss (OTL) and face-centered cubic (FCC) lattices, alongside twisting deformation under compression. Azadi et al. [13] investigated the high cycle bending fatigue properties of FDM 3D-printed ABS and PLA polymers. The results indicate that PLA exhibits superior fatigue lifetime compared to ABS, and horizontally printed specimens demonstrate higher fatigue lifetime.

Maharaj and James [14] developed a topology-optimized unit cell for the shear layer of a non-pneumatic tire, incorporating stress and buckling constraints. Using a numerical optimization framework based on the adjoint method and linear buckling analysis, the resulting cells achieved the target effective shear modulus of 10 MPa, demonstrating suitability for non-pneumatic tire applications. Similarly, Qin et al. [15] proposed a framework for designing metamaterials with an arbitrary negative Poisson's ratio (NPR) using topology optimization of triangular and rectangular unit cells. Their method employed three objective functions—maximum compliance, minimum mass, and minimum compliance variation—to generate structures with NPR values ranging from -0.3 to -0.6 , confirming close agreement between single-cell and macroscopic NPR values (error $\sim 3.3\%$). Vegiatis et al. [16] extended this approach to multi-material metamaterials with NPR, introducing a level-set-based optimization method combined with the refined level set (RLS) approach and the MBO operator for simplified multi-material topology optimization. Their framework effectively redefines the design problem of NPR metamaterials, enabling precise control over auxetic behavior across single- and multi-material systems.

Chung and Du [17] introduced a framework for topology optimization of multi-material cellular architectures to design thermal metamaterials resilient to temperature changes. Gao et al. [18] introduced a topology-guided approach to fatigue optimization, in which stress, material volume, and fatigue strength serve as key constraints, with the primary objective of reducing compliance. Expanding on this, Gao et al. [19] proposed an isogeometric topology optimization (ITO) method for the design of three-material auxetic metamaterials, enabling precise control over mechanical response and auxetic behavior across complex multi-material cellular architectures. These studies collectively highlight the growing capability of advanced topology optimization methods to generate multifunctional metamaterials with tailored mechanical and thermal properties.

Wand et al. [20] present DiffMat, a diffusion-based inverse-design model that generates microstructures directly from a target stress-strain curve. Their data-driven approach produces diverse geometries that accurately match desired energy-absorption responses, with numerical and experimental results confirming fast, reliable performance. Choudhry et al. [21] introduce two improved 2D re-entrant auxetic lattices (Type A and B) by adding vertical ligaments and fabricating them via FDM. Compression tests and FE simulations show significant enhancements— $\sim 355\%$ higher stiffness and $\sim 165\%$ greater specific energy absorption relative to standard re-entrant lattices of equal mass. They demonstrate that adjusting sub-cell geometry and thickness allows tuning stiffness, strength, energy absorption, and Poisson's ratio.

Shahmorad et al. [22] presents the design, simulation, and 3D printing of novel auxetic metamaterials, focusing on their mechanical response under impact loading. A sensitivity analysis is performed to evaluate the influence of geometric parameters on energy absorption and impact performance, showing that structural design significantly

affects dynamic behavior. Vidakis et al. [23] reported the strain rate sensitivity of five thermoplastic polymers include Poly(lactic Acid) (PLA), Acrylonitrile Butadiene-Styrene (ABS), Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG), Polyamide 6 (PA6), and Polypropylene (PP) manufactured via material extrusion. These materials reviewed under static tensile loading conditions and five different strain rates. The results showed that the strain rate sensitivity and toughness for ABS, PA6, PETG, PLA, and PP indicated the expected mechanical properties from each of the polymers under different static tensile loading conditions. In addition, PLA is highly sensitive to the strain rate.

In this study, three topology-optimized metamaterial unit cells (TV, TH, and TVH) were designed using the SIMP-based topology optimization method to investigate the influence of structural topology on mechanical behavior. The optimized cells were fabricated using material extrusion 3D printing with PLA material and experimentally evaluated under quasi-static compression and dynamic impact loading conditions. The results showed that the optimized topologies produced distinct mechanical responses: the TV structure exhibited the highest compressive load-bearing capacity, while the TH structure demonstrated the highest specific energy absorption. These findings confirm that topology optimization can be effectively used to tailor the mechanical performance of lightweight metamaterial structures for different engineering applications.

The contribution of this study does not lie in proposing a fundamentally new topology optimization algorithm beyond existing methods such as BESO, level-set methods, or machine-learning-based inverse design. Instead, the novelty lies in the application of a unified SIMP-based topology optimization framework to generate and experimentally evaluate multiple topology families with distinct mechanical responses, enabling a direct comparison of topology-dependent trade-offs between compressive strength and energy absorption.

Unlike many previous studies that focus on optimizing a single lattice geometry or a single performance objective, the present work develops three different topology-optimized cell configurations (TV, TH, and TVH) from different initial design domains under a consistent optimization framework. This allows the study to reveal how the topology optimization pathway influences the final mechanical functionality of the metamaterial.

In addition, the present study combines this comparative topology design strategy with experimental validation under both quasi-static compression and dynamic impact loading, making it possible to identify which topology is more suitable for load-bearing applications and which is more effective for energy absorption. This provides a practical design guideline for tailoring metamaterial architectures according to performance requirements.

The novelty of the present work does not lie in proposing a new topology optimization algorithm, but rather in the comparative design and experimental validation of multiple topology-optimized metamaterial configurations within a unified framework.

The main novel contributions are as follows:

- A systematic comparison of three distinct topology families (TV, TH, and TVH structures) generated from different initial design domains using the same SIMP-based optimization approach.
- Demonstration that different topology optimization pathways lead to fundamentally different mechanical responses, even under identical material and boundary conditions.
- A combined experimental evaluation under both quasi-static compression and dynamic impact loading, which is rarely addressed simultaneously in previous studies.
- Identification of a clear trade-off between compressive strength and specific energy absorption, providing a practical design guideline.

Unlike many existing studies that focus on optimizing a single geometry or a single objective, this work highlights how topology selection itself can be used as a design variable to tailor performance.

Therefore, the novelty lies in the experimentally validated, topology-dependent structure–performance relationship and comparative design methodology, rather than in algorithmic development.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Material properties

In this study, polylactic acid (PLA) was used to manufacture the test specimens. A commercial PLA filament (1.75 mm, eSUN, China) was used in this study for specimen fabrication. Although the exact chemical composition of the filament was not disclosed by the manufacturer, the mechanical properties of the printed material were experimentally characterized through compression testing prior to topology optimization. The measured elastic modulus and yield stress were then used as input parameters in the numerical analysis. It should be noted that different commercial PLA grades may exhibit different mechanical responses due to variations in formulation and processing conditions; therefore, the quantitative results presented in this work are specific to the material grade used, while the proposed design methodology remains generally applicable. Literature sources generally report the density of PLA to be around 1240 kg/m³, with a corresponding Poisson's ratio of roughly 0.36 [24,25]. To obtain the material properties, a compressive test was performed according to ASTM D695 at a loading rate of 1.3 mm/min on three 3D-printed cylindrical specimens. The specimens are shown in Fig. 1. After designing the TH, TV, and TVH cells, they were arranged next to each other, and the samples were fabricated using a Creality K1 material extrusion (MEX) 3D printer. The printing parameters were set according to the specifications listed in Table 1. These parameters were chosen based on previous studies [26, 27].

In this study, the term “cell” refers to the optimized repeating geometric element, while “metamaterial” refers to the assembled specimen composed of multiple unit cells. The term “lattice” is used only when describing the periodic arrangement of unit cells. This terminology has been unified throughout the manuscript for consistency.

2.2. Topology optimization

Topology optimization was performed using the Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) method in Abaqus. Density-based topology optimization is a widely used approach to determine the optimal material distribution. In this method, the design domain is discretized into finite elements, and each element is assigned a design variable ρ_e representing its relative density, where $0 \leq \rho_e \leq 1$. A value of 1

Fig. 1. The 3D-printed specimens for obtaining material properties.

Table 1
3D printing parameters [26,27].

Layer Hight	Nozzle temperature	Infill	3D print speed
0.2 mm	160 °C	100%	20 mm/s

indicates solid material, while 0 represents a void. SIMP approach interpolates the stiffness of each element as a function of its density according to Eq. (1) [28]:

$$E_e = \rho_e^p E_0 \quad (1)$$

In this expression, E_e denotes the effective young's modulus of the element, ρ_e^p stands for the element density, and E_0 represents the young's modulus of the solid material.

The general topology optimization problem for stiffness maximization (or compliance minimization) can be formulated as Eq. (2) [29]:

$$\text{Min } C(\rho) = F^T U(\rho) \quad (2)$$

$$V(\rho)/V_0 \leq f$$

$$0 \leq \rho_e \leq 1$$

Where $C(\rho)$ is the total compliance (objective), F is the global load vector, $U(\rho)$ is the displacement vector obtained from $K(\rho)U = F$, $V(\rho)$ is the total material volume, V_0 is the design domain volume, and f is the prescribed volume fraction.

For the topology optimization and unit cell design, three different initial geometries were considered. These geometries, shown in Fig. 2, were selected based on a standard compression test specimen, such that their arrangement would form a standard test geometry. The standard specimen was defined as a cubic geometry with dimensions of $70 \times 70 \times 4$ mm. Accordingly, the initial geometries were sized so that three cells were aligned vertically (TV), three cells horizontally (TH), and nine cells in total in both vertical and horizontal directions (TVH), producing the standard test specimen.

The material properties, including elastic modulus, yield stress, density, and Poisson's ratio, were assigned to PLA based on the standard compression test described in the prior section. A uniform compressive load was then applied to the specimen, while the opposite surface was fully constrained. The loading conditions are illustrated in Fig. 3. In the present study, topology optimization was performed under quasi-static compressive loading to provide a computationally efficient basis for identifying favorable material distributions. Although this approach captures the dominant compressive load paths, it does not directly account for inertia effects, strain-rate sensitivity, or multi-axial stress states that may arise under impact loading. Therefore, the optimized topologies were subsequently evaluated experimentally under dynamic loading. Future work may extend the optimization framework to include nonlinear dynamic or multi-axial loading conditions for improved impact-specific design.

The finite element model assumed the PLA material to be homogeneous, isotropic, and linear elastic, with material properties obtained experimentally from compression tests of 3D-printed specimens. Although FDM-printed polymers may exhibit anisotropic behavior, the isotropic assumption is widely adopted in topology optimization studies for computational efficiency and design comparison purposes. A mesh convergence, as it is shown in Fig. 4, was performed based on the von Mises stress, and an element size of 0.08 mm was selected as the converged solution.

The SIMP-based topology optimization strategy was selected because it provides an efficient framework for identifying the optimal material distribution within a fixed design domain while satisfying mass constraints. This method is particularly suitable for metamaterial design because it enables the generation of lightweight yet mechanically efficient architectures. In the present work, the optimization aimed to minimize compliance (maximize stiffness) while reducing stress

Fig. 2. Initial geometry for designing (a) TV, (b) TH, and (c) TVH.

Fig. 3. Loading conditions (a) TV, (b) TH, and (c) TVH.

Fig. 4. Mesh convergence.

concentration under mass constraints. In other word, the objective was to reduce stress concentration while minimizing mass, thereby

improving structural efficiency and enhancing energy absorption potential. Different mass constraints were examined to evaluate the balance between material reduction and structural integrity. The selected boundary conditions reproduced the intended compressive loading conditions so that the resulting topologies would be relevant for experimental evaluation.

The minimization of von Mises stress was selected as the objective function because it is a well-established approach in topology optimization for achieving uniform stress distribution and maximizing structural load-bearing capacity. Directly optimizing energy absorption or plateau stress is considerably more challenging within a standard FEA-based topology optimization framework because these quantities depend on nonlinear material behavior, large deformations, and the full force–displacement response, which are computationally expensive and difficult to converge in an optimization loop.

By minimizing von Mises stress, we ensure that the structure maintains high stiffness and avoids stress concentrations, which indirectly contributes to improved energy absorption under compression and impact. After the optimization, the energy absorption performance of each topology was evaluated experimentally, providing direct verification of the effectiveness of the designs for energy-dissipating applications.

This approach has been widely adopted in the literature [5,21],

where the optimization objective focuses on stress or compliance minimization, followed by experimental evaluation of energy absorption.

For each initial geometry, several optimizations run with different mass constraints were performed to identify the most efficient configuration. For example, for the TH specimen, topology optimization was conducted using final mass constraints of $\leq 70\%$, $\leq 50\%$, and $\leq 25\%$ of the initial mass. The penalization factor in the SIMP interpolation scheme was set to 3 to ensure clear separation between solid and void regions.

2.3. 3D-printing

After designing the TH, TV, and THV cells, they were arranged next to each other, and the samples were then fabricated using a material extrusion (MEX) 3D printer. The 3D printing parameters were set according to the specifications listed in Table 1.

The dimensions of the initial sample significantly influence the optimization results, as do the boundary conditions and, in general, any factor that alters the stress contour. However, if all parameters are kept constant and the dimensions are uniformly scaled in all three directions, the response remains unchanged. Therefore, after the optimization process, the cells were uniformly scaled and considered in a larger size for designing the impact test specimens. The printed samples are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 for the compressive and impact experiments, respectively.

2.4. Compressive test

Uniaxial compression testing was carried out in accordance with ASTM D695 at a rate of 1.3 mm/min. Prior studies have applied similar standards and loading protocols to characterize the mechanical properties of 3D-printed PLA metamaterials [30–33].

Initially, a uniaxial compression test was performed to determine the specific energy absorption (SEA) of the specimens. The resulting SEA value was subsequently used to adjust the impact test settings. Therefore, the compression test was continued until the nominal stress–strain curve, after the relatively flat plateau region, exhibited a sudden increase. This point corresponds to the onset of cell densification. In other words, the test was terminated at the beginning of the densification region, marking the end of the plateau zone. The specific energy absorption (SEA) was then calculated from the force–displacement curve according to Eq. (3).

$$SEA = \frac{\int_0^x F(Z)dZ}{m} \quad (3)$$

In this equation, m refers to the mass of the specimen in grams, F to the applied force in newtons, and z to the displacement in millimeters.

The displacement at the beginning is set to zero, and integration is carried out to the maximum value of x on the force–displacement curve.

The specific energy absorption (SEA) of the specimens was determined following widely accepted procedures in the literature. The energy absorbed by each specimen under quasi-static axial compression was calculated by integrating the area under the force–displacement curve up to the maximum displacement recorded. The SEA was subsequently obtained by normalizing the absorbed energy by the specimen mass, as described in previous studies [34–36].

For instance, [34] investigated bio-inspired corrugated CFRP crash boxes and determined the SEA using the force–displacement integral divided by the specimen mass, demonstrating the effectiveness of this method in lightweight composite structures. Similarly, [35] studied polyurethane foam-filled metal/composite hybrid structures, in which the total absorbed energy was computed from the load–displacement curve and normalized by mass to obtain SEA. Finally, [36] evaluated fiberglass-filled crash boxes and used the same force–displacement integral approach to determine both total energy absorption and SEA, highlighting its applicability for analyzing deformation patterns and crashworthiness.

In the present study, the same methodology was applied: the force–displacement diagrams obtained from quasi-static axial compression tests were integrated to compute absorbed energy, and the SEA of each specimen was calculated as the absorbed energy divided by its mass.

2.5. Impact test

To investigate the material's mechanical response under dynamic conditions, an impact test was performed by dropping a projectile from a specified height onto the specimen. In this scenario, the projectile's kinetic energy upon impact induces deformation or fracture in the specimen, enabling the absorbed energy to be quantified. The impact energy in this test, according to Equation 4, is a function of the projectile's mass and the drop height.

$$E = m \times g \times h \quad (4)$$

In this equation, E represents the impact energy in joules, m is the mass of the projectile, fixed at 7.5 kg because of the constraints of the testing equipment, g is the gravitational acceleration in meters per second squared, and h is the drop height, which was set to 3 and 5 cm. The test was repeated twice for each specimen to ensure repeatability. All impact tests were conducted in accordance with the ASTM D5420 standard.

In particular, this method was described in [37], where a projectile is dropped from a specified height onto the specimen, and the kinetic energy at impact induces deformation or fracture, allowing the absorbed energy to be quantified. Similarly, recent studies on composite energy absorbers have employed drop-weight impact tests to assess dynamic

Fig. 5. Metamaterial designs for compression experiments.

Fig. 6. Impact-tested metamaterial configurations.

response and energy absorption characteristics under controlled conditions [38].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Material properties

Findings from the compression test for the standard samples are presented in Fig. 7. Based on these results, the mechanical properties of the PLA material were calculated. Based on the obtained data, the young's modulus and the yield stress were calculated to be approximately 1100 MPa and 52 MPa, respectively. In a previous investigation, the yield stress and young's modulus were determined using a comparable experimental approach, and the findings were consistent with those of the present study [27]. These properties were subsequently used for the topology optimization process.

To quantitatively evaluate the strain-rate sensitivity of the printed PLA structures, additional compression tests were conducted at loading rates of 1, 1.3, and 1.6 mm/min and the corresponding stress-strain responses are shown in Fig. 8. The results indicate that the mechanical response of the material changes with loading rate. Although the initial peak stress remained relatively similar, the post-yield and densification behavior showed noticeable differences. In particular, the specimens tested at 1.6 mm/min exhibited higher stress levels in the densification region compared with those tested at 1 mm/min, indicating an increase

in apparent stiffness with increasing loading rate.

These results confirm the strain-rate sensitivity of PLA, where increasing the loading rate modifies the deformation response and enhances the resistance of the structure during progressive compression. This rate-dependent behavior explains, at least in part, the differences observed between quasi-static and impact performance in the optimized metamaterial structures.

3.2. Topology optimization

As previously described, topology optimization was performed for three structures, namely TV, TH, and TVH, under different mass constraints. Table 2 presents the optimization results for the TV sample. As shown in the table, the optimization was first carried out with remaining mass constraints of 70%, 50%, and 30% of the initial mass. Subsequently, a symmetry constraint was applied to each case. According to the results, when the 30% mass constraint and the symmetry condition were applied simultaneously, the resulting design was no longer continuous and thus could not be manufactured. Therefore, this case was excluded from further consideration. On the other hand, for the 50% mass constraint, the optimized structures with and without the symmetry condition exhibited identical responses and remained fully continuous; hence, these configurations were selected. Under the 30% mass constraint, the optimization process removed excessive material, resulting in a highly porous and partially discontinuous geometry.

Fig. 7. Stress-strain curve obtained from compressive test.

Fig. 8. Stress–strain curves of the printed PLA specimens under different compression loading rates.

Although the volume reduction target was achieved, the resulting structure lacked sufficient structural continuity for effective load transfer and was not suitable for fabrication by material extrusion. Therefore, this configuration was excluded from the experimental phase.

Similarly, Table 3 presents the optimization results for the TH sample. For this configuration, topology optimization was carried out under 50% and 30% mass constraints, with a symmetry condition applied in both cases. Based on the results, the design satisfying the 30% mass constraint and the symmetry condition was selected as the optimal configuration.

The printing angle of the bases or struts in 3D printing is critical. If this angle is $<45^\circ$, support structures are required for fabrication. Since the cells are arranged adjacent to each other, forming a complex geometry, removing these supports from the sample is challenging. Therefore, the sample with a 30% weight constraint, after applying symmetry about the y-axis, was found to have strut angles unsuitable for 3D printing. Consequently, optimization was performed with symmetry about the x-axis, and this configuration was deemed suitable for fabrication.

Additionally, the TVH sample was optimized under 50% and 30% constraints. Since the 30% constraint did not yield acceptable results, optimization was also performed with a 40% constraint. Table 4 provides the results. Consistent with the figure and similar to the previous case, the sample with the 40% constraint and symmetry about the x-axis was selected.

After designing the cells, four cells were arranged adjacent to each other in the vertical and horizontal directions and around each strut, and enclosed within a wall. Compression and impact test specimens were then fabricated, as shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Fig. 9 presents the Von Mises stress distribution for the selected specimens.

3.3. Compressive test

Compression tests were conducted on the functionally graded samples. Since the samples have variable cross-sections, force–displacement curves were obtained for these specimens, as shown in Fig. 10. In other studies, force–displacement curves have been used for porous structures, or the stress has been calculated assuming a fully solid cross-section [30].

It should be noted that the numerical simulations were performed on the individual unit-cell level for topology optimization purposes, while the experimental tests were conducted on assembled specimens

consisting of multiple optimized cells. Therefore, the finite element model was intended to provide a comparative design evaluation rather than an exact quantitative prediction of the full structural response.

According to the obtained results, the TV, TVH, and TH samples exhibited the highest forces, respectively. On average, the TV samples withstood a force of 1600 N. In another study, among the designed and introduced cells, three types—honeycomb, cubic, and tetrahedral—were selected, arranged adjacently, and a functionally graded structure with dimensions similar to those in the present study was fabricated. However, the maximum compressive force that these structures could withstand was 1400 N [27]. This indicates the superiority of the design achieved through the optimization approach.

In Table 5, the specimens' characteristics, along with the energy absorption and specific energy absorption, are presented. The energy absorbed can be determined by integrating the force–displacement curve.

For each specimen configuration, three samples were tested under identical conditions for both compression and impact experiments. The reported values represent the average results, and the deviations were calculated from the repeated measurements to evaluate experimental repeatability. Although the number of repetitions was limited, the experimental trends were consistent across the tested samples, showing the same ranking in mechanical performance among the investigated topologies.

Since the specific energy absorption of the solid specimens was computed as 1810 J/kg, it can be concluded that the TV and TH structures exhibited higher specific energy absorption. However, the TVH specimen showed a lower specific energy absorption. The highest specific energy absorption was observed in the TH specimen, exceeding the values reported for the structures in previous studies [39–41].

3.4. Impact test

The force–displacement curves obtained from the impact tests for the three designed test samples are displayed in Fig. 11.

According to the results, although the TV specimen demonstrated the best load-bearing capacity under quasi-static compression, it recorded the lowest peak force in the impact test. This discrepancy can arise from several factors, as outlined below.

First, the mechanical response of many materials varies significantly under high loading rates. Depending on the material and loading conditions, the strength may decrease, or the failure mode may change under dynamic loading. PLA is a strain-rate-sensitive polymer, and its

Table 2
Topology optimization results for TV sample.

Weight constraint	Symmetry constraint	Result
%70	-	
%50	-	
%50	symmetry about the y-axis	
%30	-	
%30	symmetry about the y-axis	

mechanical behavior is known to change with increasing loading rate. Numerous studies have reported that higher strain rates increase the strength and elastic modulus of PLA—meaning that the material often becomes mechanically "stiffer" under rapid loading [42]. However, other investigations have shown that during impact loading, PLA simultaneously exhibits reduced plastic deformation and toughness, leading to more brittle, localized failure and a mechanical response that is markedly different—and in some cases inferior—to that observed under quasi-static loading [43].

For FDM/FFF-printed PLA structures, manufacturing parameters such as printing orientation, infill density, layer height, and extrusion temperature also influence the strain-rate sensitivity and overall

dynamic behavior [44]. Consequently, the response of additively manufactured PLA structures under impact can differ substantially from their quasi-static performance.

Additionally, under slow loading conditions, cellular or lattice structures may undergo gradual compaction or stable deformation, allowing them to sustain higher loads. In contrast, impact loading can trigger premature local buckling or brittle, layer-by-layer failure, which significantly reduces the instantaneous load-carrying capacity [45,46].

Moreover, the observed behavior is not solely related to the brittle nature of PLA. The structural topology also plays an important role in determining the deformation mode under different loading conditions. The TV structure provides efficient vertical load-transfer paths under

Table 3
Topology optimization results for TH sample.

Weight constraint	Symmetry constraint	Result	Weight constraint	Symmetry constraint	Result
50	-				
30	symmetry about the y-axis				

quasi-static compression, resulting in higher compressive strength. However, under impact loading, this same topology tends to concentrate stresses locally and limits progressive deformation, which reduces its energy absorption capability. In contrast, the TH structure allows more gradual collapse and better stress redistribution during impact, resulting in improved impact performance.

Energy absorption was evaluated by integrating the force–displacement curve. Based on the mass of each structure, the specific energy absorption was also computed for all specimens and is presented in Table 6.

For comparison, recent studies on 3D-printed lattice structures have reported specific energy absorption values significantly lower than those obtained here. For instance, auxetic lattices exhibited SEA in the range of approximately 5–10 kJ/kg [21], and Voronoi honeycomb structures showed much lower total energy absorption values [47]. Similarly, aluminum auxetic metamaterials demonstrated SEA of only 0.5–6.8 kJ/kg [48], further highlighting the relatively high specific energy absorption achieved in the present work.

To further evaluate the performance of the proposed topology-optimized metamaterial structures, a comparison was conducted with previously reported 3D-printed lattice and metamaterial designs.

Compared with conventional PLA-based lattice structures, the proposed designs demonstrate competitive energy absorption performance. For instance, Choudhry et al. [21] reported that improved re-entrant auxetic PLA lattices fabricated via FDM achieved significant enhancement in stiffness and specific energy absorption compared with standard re-entrant lattices, with SEA values generally in the range of a few kJ/kg. Similarly, Prajapati et al. [8] showed that hybrid TPU-based

metamaterial cells improved stiffness and damping behavior through geometric modification. In the present work, the TH structure achieved a specific energy absorption of 4.89 kJ/kg under compression, which is within the upper range of values reported for polymer-based lattice structures.

Under dynamic loading conditions, Zhang et al. [11] investigated wavy-wall metamaterials under static and dynamic compression and reported that geometric parameters significantly affect energy absorption performance, although the energy dissipation under impact loading was lower than under quasi-static loading. Likewise, Hu et al. [9] demonstrated that the number of cells and architecture strongly influence compressive strength and energy absorption in additively manufactured metamaterials. The present results confirm these observations, showing that optimized topology directly affects the balance between compressive load capacity and impact energy absorption.

In addition, Asman et al. [12] reported that metallic lattice structures fabricated by selective laser melting exhibited higher specific energy absorption due to improved structural continuity. Although the present study uses a single-material PLA system produced by material extrusion, the optimized TH topology demonstrated favorable energy absorption characteristics while maintaining a lightweight structure, highlighting the efficiency of the topology optimization approach.

Overall, the comparison with previous studies [7,9,11,12,21] indicates that the proposed topology-optimized designs achieve mechanical performance comparable to or better than many conventionally designed polymer metamaterials. This demonstrates that topology optimization can provide an effective route for improving the energy absorption efficiency of lightweight additively manufactured structures.

Table 4
Topology optimization results for TVH sample.

Weight constraint	Symmetry constraint	Result
50	-	
40	-	
40	symmetry about the x-axis	
40	symmetry about the y-axis	
30	-	

Due to differences in testing configurations and impact energy normalization methods, direct quantitative comparison of impact-specific energy absorption with previous studies remains difficult.

The proposed topology-optimized structures are particularly suitable

for applications requiring lightweight energy-absorbing components, such as automotive crashworthiness systems, protective packaging, impact protection layers, and lightweight protective structures. In these applications, the ability to tailor the balance between load-bearing

Fig. 9. The von Mises stress distribution for (a) TV, (b) TH, and (c) TVH.

Fig. 10. Fore-extension obtained from compressive test.

Table 5
Energy absorption of structures.

Cell	Weight (gr)	Energy absorption (J)	Specific energy absorption (J/kg)
TV	1.92	6.9 ± 2.4	3614.5 ± 1200.7
TH	1.42	6.9 ± 1.1	4885.2 ± 831.8
TVH	1.72	1.5 ± 0.3	829.4 ± 208.6

capacity and energy absorption is highly desirable. The results of this study showed that different optimized topologies provide distinct mechanical responses, allowing the structural configuration to be selected based on the required performance. For example, the TV structure exhibited higher compressive strength, while the TH structure demonstrated superior specific energy absorption, making it more suitable for impact mitigation applications.

Compared with traditional honeycomb or metal foam structures, the proposed designs offer several advantages. First, topology optimization enables targeted material distribution, which improves structural efficiency by placing material only in mechanically effective regions. Second, the use of material extrusion additive manufacturing allows the fabrication of customized geometries that are difficult to achieve with conventional manufacturing methods. In addition, compared with

metallic foams, the proposed PLA-based metamaterial structures provide lower weight, easier fabrication, and lower manufacturing cost, while still achieving favorable energy absorption performance. These characteristics make the proposed structures promising candidates for lightweight protective applications where tailored mechanical performance is required.

4. Conclusion

The comparative evaluation of the three topology-optimized PLA structures (TV, TH, and TVH) demonstrates how architectural design governs mechanical performance under compression and impact loading. When the results are expressed in percentage differences, the following key findings emerge:

- Despite a 50% weight reduction, the TV structure maintains high compressive strength and balanced impact performance.
- With only 30% weight reduction, the TH structure delivers exceptional impact energy absorption, making it the most suitable option for high-impact applications.
- The TVH structure, with 40% weight reduction, provides the highest impact load capacity, though with lower specific energy absorption in compression.

These percentage-based comparative results emphasize that topology optimization enables tailored mechanical responses, allowing each structure to be matched to specific engineering needs, such as maximizing energy absorption or achieving lightweight high-strength performance.

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Table 6
The specific energy absorption from the impact test.

Cell	Weight (gr)	Energy absorption (J)	Specific energy absorption (J/Kg)
TV	8.93	910.04±6.36	88,784.88±620.97
TH	10.25	1310.54±345.88	146,757.00±38,732.40
TVH	8.87	563.11±46.17	63,485.58±5205.52

Fig. 11. Force-displacement from impact test.

Code availability

Not applicable.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Amir Shahmorad: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Majid Rajabi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Ramin Hashemi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

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